

**MORPHOFUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES OF VASCULARIZATION OF DORSAL ROOT GANGLIA.
SPECIFICITY OF PRECAPILLARY ARTERIOLES UNDER LIGHT AND ELECTRON
MICROSCOPIC STUDY**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199127>

Abstract

We present the morphological (histological and ultrastructural) peculiarities of vascularization of dorsal root ganglia, especially the specific properties of precapillary arterioles under light and electron microscopic study. Considered the vascularization of the dorsal root ganglia was abundantly than other part of peripheral nerve because of primary sensory neurons participated in neurotransmission required more supplying with blood. The research performed on male rat's dorsal root ganglia that embedded in Epon Araldite blocks according to general methods accepted in microscopy. The current study demonstrates structure, source, direction, composition of dorsal root ganglia supplying vessels.

Keywords: dorsal root ganglia, blood vessels, precapillary arterioles, rat

Introduction. The study of blood supply of peripheral nerve is important, because of the blood vessels participant of providing blood transport, metabolic exchange, as well as immunological function, humoral regulation of it (1). Any disorder in the blood supply of the peripheral nerves may lead to motor and sensory disintegration due to degenerative changes in these fibers (2). The inseparable structural component of peripheral nerve is dorsal root ganglia (DRG), situated on dorsal root of spinal cord. DRG relays all sensory information (exteroceptive, interoceptive, proprioceptive) from outer and inner environment of body directly to the central nervous system (3, 4). The DRG, that clinical target for pain control placed out of the blood-brain barrier. Because of the nociceptor primary sensory neurons play a key role in eliciting pain (5), as well as regulate nociceptive transmission (6). At that point, different molecules and substances circulating in the vascular network can directly inflow to DRG and influence its structural components. Any disturbance in the extra and intraganglionic vessels, especially supplying vessels lead to dysfunction of organ. The blood vessels (arteriole, precapillary arteriole, capillary, postcapillary and collecting venules) comprising the microcirculation system (MS) have their own ultrastructural features to regulate the local blood circulation, which are sometimes sharply different from each other (7). In this re-

gard, precapillary arterioles located in a strategic topographical position are of special importance in the regulation of both transcapillary and supracapillary blood flow within dorsal root ganglia.

Aim of study was to explore the morphological properties (structural and ultrastructural composition), direction source and branches of vessels, especially precapillary arterioles of dorsal root ganglia.

Methods. The objects of research were dorsal root ganglions taken from 20 white rats with weight of 180-200 gram. The animals purchased from Science Research laboratory and grew up in specific pathogen-free conditions. All procedures in experiments complied with the Principles of Laboratory and Animal Care established by the Azerbaijan Medical University. The rats one by one laid down in a supine position on a pad, first thoracic cavity was opened with parasternal incisions under deep ketamine / xylazine (100/10mg/kg) anaesthesia; the vessels of objects were washed during 1 minute at a pressure of 80 mm Hg with Hank's solution containing 500 ml physiological salt solution +50V heparin +1 ml 1% papaverine hydrochloride by catheter administered to the initial part of aortic arch; then research animals fixated with vascular perfusion with 2,5% glutaraldehyde solution prepared in 0,1M phosphate buffer (pH=7,4). The perfusion lasted 25 minutes at a pressure of 80 mm Hg. Then experimental animals (rats) subdivided into 2 groups. The first group (10 rats)

animals after opening abdominal cavity the thoracic and lumbar ganglions removed from soft tissue, then did the postfixation in 1% osmium acid solution in phosphate buffer, and prepared Spurr and Epon - Araldite blocks according to general methods accepted in microscopy (8). Obtained from blocks on ultratome LKB-III the semithin (1-2 μm) sections were stained with methylene blue, azure II and basic fuchsin (9); gained the silver and gold ultrathin sections from same blocks first painted with 2% uranyl acetate solution, then in 0.6% lead citrate made in NaOH 0.1N solution. After ultrathin sections examined under the Transmission Electron Microscope (JEM-1400, Japan) at an accelerating voltage of 80-100 kV and received the electronograms. This procedure continued until the block had been used.

As well as into the ascending aorta of other 10 white rats were administered ink solutions dissolved in 10% gelatine until it is outflow from vena cava inferior. Afterwards purchased from rats the research specimens

(spinal cord, spinal roots, dorsal root ganglions, spinal nerves) fixated in 10% formalin solution and being frozen in cryostat, then received total sections in 100-150 μm thickness. Both semithin and total sections were examined at Latimet (Leitz) microscope and captured the necessary parts of the images by Pixera (USA) digital camera and saved in computer.

Results. In comparative study of the parts of peripheral nerve revealed the richly vascularization of dorsal root ganglia than dorsal, ventral roots and along the spinal nerve (10). The DRG that composed of cell bodies of primary sensory neurons, situated on dorsal root (shown by double blue arrow on lower right side of fig.1) of spinal cord. Among primary sensory neurons visible nerve fibers, lumen of vessels and capsule (shown by red arrow) covering from all side DRG. On superior central part of slide indicated by single blue arrow is ventral root of spinal cord. Later both root joined and formatted the spinal nerve.

Figure 1. Histological semithin section of dorsal root ganglion with surrounding structural elements. Single blue arrow show the ventral root, by double blue arrow indicated the dorsal root, by red arrow mentioned capsule of DRG. Abbreviation: A-arterial vessel, V-venous vessel. The explanation given in text. Stain: azure II and basic fuchsin. Scale bar 100 μm .

The study of semi-thin sections obtained from Epon-Araldite blocks prepared after taking together the DRG and surrounding connective tissue elements at the level of the intervertebral foramen shows that neither the capsule of DRG nor the layer covering the initial parts of the spinal nerves contain only their own vascu-

lar networks. The vessels participating in the vascularization of the mentioned organ should be divided topographically into only two groups, external and internal (11). On mentioned figure within the capsule of DRG clear seen that there are no profiles of vessels belonging to the microcirculation system, especially capillaries, which are considered exchange vessels.

Figure 2. Cryostatic section of dorsal root ganglion vessels was revealed with the ink solution (dissolved in 10% gelatin) injected into the ascending aorta after fixation by the perfusion method . The explanation is given in text. Abbreviation: A-arterial vessel, V-venous vessel, CN-capillary network. Scale bar 100µm.

All of the blood vessels located in the immediate vicinity of capsule from both side (outer and inner) are either arterial vessels (A) or venules (V). The larger luminal diameter of venules and the wide thickness wall of arterial vessels within connective tissue elements of the initial part of the spinal nerve clearly visible on slide (fig.1).

After fixation by the intravascular perfusion method, then injected into the ascending aorta the ink

that dissolved in a 10% gelatin solution, later from tissue specimen prepared the total sections in a cryostat. In this section determined the composition, size, course of all vessels, especially microvessels included in the internal vascular network, also the smallest branch they given, as well as the the mutual relations with structural components of organ. That is, the arterioles separated from the arteries located in the external area of the organ transitively pierce the capsule of the ganglion and gives rise to the internal vascular network (fig.2).

Figure 3. Cryostatic section of dorsal root ganglion vessels was revealed with the ink solution (dissolved in 10% gelatin) injected into the ascending aorta after fixation by the perfusion method. The explanation is given in text. Abbreviation: A-arterial vessel, V-venous vessel. Scale bar in all slide 100µm.

The study of thick cryostat sections shows on slide 2 from both poles of ganglion the arterial vessels pierced the capsule and directed to the central part of organ, then branched to the arterioles and precapillary arterioles. The arterial vessels accompanied by venous vessels, but the direction of venous vessels from central to the periphery - out of center. The capillary network arising from precapillary arterioles created inner vascular network of organ. The venules originating from the intraganglionar vascular network still pass through the capsule and connect to the venous vessels located around the ganglion (Fig. 2).

As can be seen, three optical sections (Fig. 3A, 3B, 3C) obtained from the same total section with the help

of the microscrew of the light microscope. In Fig. 3A are clearly visible in the superior middle part the intra-capsular arteriole, the branches from it; in the middle part deeper located the capillary loops obscure visible; but the collecting venule formatted from the latter (lower middle) located in the superficial layer visible legible. In Fig. 3B, the precapillary arterioles branching off from the arteriole, and the loop-shaped nets formed by the capillaries originating from them around the nerve cells (see below), are clearly visible, while the collecting venule itself appears somewhat hazy. In Fig. 3C, while deep vascular nets are clearly visible, postcapillary venules, which are involved in its formation, along with the collecting venule, appear hazy.

Figure 4. A Cryostatic section of dorsal root ganglion vessels was revealed with the ink solution (dissolved in 10% gelatin) injected into the ascending aorta after fixation by the perfusion method. Branches to middle size diameter arterioles in the ascending and descending direction indicated by red arrows; B Histological semithin section of dorsal root ganglion with supplying vessels after fixation by the perfusion method. Stain: azure II and basic fuchsine. The explanation is given in text. Scale bar: A 100μm; B 50μm.

Thus, by moving the microscrew of the microscope, in the total sections, the course of most of the intracapsular vessels starting from arterioles to collecting venules, the forms of the capillary network they form, their morphometric measurements, shape, direction of blood within organ etc. it is possible to determine.

Arterioles supplying the DRG by piercing the capsule firstly give branches to middle size diameter arterioles in the ascending and descending direction (indicated by arrows in fig.4A). The indicated branches join

end-to-end with arterioles from other sources and together with collateral branch connections along their course form the intraorgan subcapsular vascular network. After giving subcapsular branches, the continuation of arterioles goes between glial covers of nerve cells or nerve fibers mainly in longitudinal, as well as in arcuate directions and gives branches to different surfaces. One of the indicators of the arcuate course of intraganglionic arterioles is the appearance of free luminal profiles in different shapes in the same semithin section (fig. 4B).

Figure 5. A Histological semithin section of dorsal root ganglion with supplying vessels after fixation by the perfusion method; B Cryostatic section of arterial vessels and precapillary of dorsal root ganglion was revealed with the ink solution (dissolved in 10% gelatin) injected into the ascending aorta after fixation by the perfusion method. The explanation is given in text. Abbreviation: A-arterial vessel, P-precapillary arteriole, N-primary sensory neuron, NF – nerve fibers. Scale bar: A 20μm; B 20μm.

Arterioles starting the intracapsular vascular network (indicated in A) during their course give rise to precapillary arterioles (shown by P), which in the organization of their walls have cells with the ability to contract (fig. 5A). In most cases, the luminal diameter of initial part of precapillary arterioles does not exceed 4-5 μm (shown by arrow).

Both small-diameter arterioles (shown by A) and precapillary arterioles (shown by P) depart from their sources at a right angle reminiscent of the letter T from intraganglionic arterioles (shown by arrow in fig.5B). Another characteristic feature of the described areas is

Figure 6. Comparative electron microscopic view of precapillary A and capillary B of dorsal root ganglion. TEM. The explanation given in the text. Stain: uranyl acetate and lead citrate. Magnification: A 25000 times, B 20000 times. Abbreviation: END- endoneurium, PMC-primitive muscle cells, P-pericyte, Er- erythrocyte, E – endothelial cells, MNF – myelinated nerve fibers, N-primary sensory neuron.

The wall of precapillary arteriole lined from inner side by endothelial cells supporting with basal lamina. Unlike to small sized arterioles in the subendothelial areas of precapillary arterioles none found the elastic surface remnants. The periendothelial cells of precapillary arterioles are a transition between pericytes (present in wall of capillary) and differentiated smooth muscle cells (present in small sized arterioles), it is more appropriate to call them primitive muscle cells (shown on fig.6A in PMC). Thus, primitive muscle cells are found along the entire course of precapillary arterioles and local flow of blood to internal vascular network of organ regulated depend on contractile ability of that cells.

After branching of precapillary arterioles from arterioles, although the luminal diameter of their doubles, ultrastructurally, there are no noticeable changes in the structures of cellular elements involved in the organization of their wall.

Generally, despite the small diameter of precapillary arterioles, their lumen are surrounded by 3 or 4 endothelial cells (fig.6A), but the number of endothelial cells in capillary vessels of almost the same diameter does not exceed 1-2. Also the central parts of the endothelial cells of precapillary, where the nucleus is located, and the peripheral parts that joined one with other are 1.5-2 times thicker than the capillaries (Fig.6B). The study of longitudinal and transversal sections from the areas where precapillary arterioles pass

the detection of differentiated muscle cells at the branching of small-diameter arterioles, and round depressions for the accommodation of primitive muscle cells (PMC) around the splitting of precapillaries (fig.5B). The last feature is more clearly noticeable along almost all courses of small-diameter arterioles separated from the main arterioles.

Under electron microscopic observation revealed some peculiarities of precapillary arterioles, that differentiated it from capillary and small sized arterioles. On fig.6 shown comparative ultrastructure of precapillary arterioles (fig.6A) and capillary (fig.6B).

into the capillary network shows that primitive muscle cells are replaced by pericyte.

Ultrastructurally noticeable features of primitive muscle cells are significant increase in the number of mitochondria compared to pericytes, both around the nucleus and in the peripheral parts. What is interesting is that while mitochondria occupy the central parts in primitive muscle cells, but actin-myosin complex and cytoskeletal elements predominate in the parts close to the plasmalemma of those cells. Therefore, compared to the differentiated muscle cells, are clearly visible relatively light, but compared to the pericytes the dark band-shaped areas.

Conclusions. Finally, it should be noted that branching from arterioles at a right angle, the small luminal diameter of the initial parts, and the location of primitive muscle cells with the ability to accumulate in the periendothelial area throughout their course indicate that precapillary arterioles play an important role in the regulation of blood circulation in dorsal root ganglia.

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This work is implemented basing on financial support of the Science Development Foundation under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Grant № EIF-2011-1(3)-82/44/3-M-6.